

REGIONAL ELECTION COMMISSION'S STRATEGY IN INCREASING POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN ELECTIONS IN CIANJUR REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study is entitled "The Strategy of the Regional General Election Commission in Increasing Political Participation in the General Election in Cianjur Regency." The background of this research is the relatively low political participation rate in Cianjur Regency, which reached only 75.7%, falling short of the national target of 80%. This study aims to describe and analyze the strategies implemented by the Regional General Election Commission (KPU Daerah) to increase political participation in the general election, as well as to identify the obstacles encountered during the implementation of these strategies. The research applies Chandler's strategic formulation theory and uses a qualitative descriptive method. Data were collected through literature study, observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis was conducted using data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The findings indicate that in the strategic formulation and long-term goal phase, the KPU Daerah implemented political education programs targeting first-time voters. In the action phase, strategies included the Desa Peduli Pemilu program, and the use of both social and traditional media. In the resource allocation phase, training programs were provided for temporary election officials (badan adhoc). However, the KPU Daerah faced several obstacles, including geographical challenges, low public trust, and limited human resources.

Keywords: General Election Commission Strategy, Political Participation, General Election

1. INTRODUCTION

General Elections are a very crucial aspect in the administration of a nation and state. The public knows and understands in detail the candidates who will compete. (Fadli et al., 2018) Elections are a legitimate mechanism to replace incumbent leaders. In addition, elections also function as a form of evaluation from the public on the performance of a leader during his tenure. General Elections are a process to elect individuals who will occupy certain political positions.

Democracy is a process of political methods with performance patterns to determine political leaders. People in a country have the right to choose one of the

political leaders according to their conscience, Nugroho 2015 in (Moento et al., 2019). In a life, democracy refers to a form of government that was initially opposed to its existence, because the rules in it often cause conflict. Over time, this system is increasingly seen as the most appropriate and appropriate system for all political institutional structures as well as elements of today's society. Based on UNESCO's research, it is concluded that democracy is a well-structured pattern in all political processes when compared to other systems (Muslih, 2012).

(Budiardjo, 2017) Political participation is the activity of a person or group of people to actively participate in political life, including by electing state leaders and, directly or indirectly, influencing government policies (public policy). These activities include actions such as voting in elections. According to Ramlan Subakti in (Suharyanto, 2014) Political participation is an activity that involves the submission of demands and the implementation of rights and obligations in a country, which are regulated by regulations. The principle of participation encourages every individual to exercise their rights in expressing their opinions related to the decision-making process related to the interests of the community, both directly and indirectly, Fitriani (2018) in (Moento et al., 2019). Political participation refers to the involvement of each individual from various elements of the political system, such as voters who participate by casting their votes, or state officials who participate in setting regulations in their territory. Citizen participation in General Elections (Elections) is a form of active contribution to a democratic system of government. In the election process, the role of the state institution that regulates and supervises, namely the General Election Commission (KPU), is very important, both at the central and regional levels.

The KPU is an institution authorized to organize the General Election process, be it the election of President and Vice President, Legislative Election, and the Election of Regional Heads and Deputy Regional Heads (Pilkada) in Indonesia. The KPU has an obligation to realize community participation to support the implementation of clean, honest, and fair elections, in accordance with the spirit of democracy and local wisdom of the Indonesian nation. To encourage a good level of political participation in the election implementation process, the KPU has the task of socializing prospective voters. These tasks are carried out in stages by the Central KPU, Provincial KPUD, and Regency/City KPUD in accordance with General Election Commission regulations Number 9 of 2022. In the context of the Regency/City, the KPUD is responsible for building the political awareness of the community, including the Cianjur Regency KPUD.

In this case, the Cianjur Regency KPUD has carried out various political strategies to increase community participation in order to achieve the expected targets. The General Election Commission of the Cianjur Regency KPUD held an Open Plenary Meeting to conduct the Recapitulation and Determination of the Permanent Voter List (DPT) for the 2024 General Election (Election) at the Cianjur Regency level which took place at Pangrango Hall Hotel Cianjur on Wednesday,

June 21, 2023. The data can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 1. Daftar Pemilih Tetap (DPT)

No	Kecamatan	Jumlah Desa	Jumlah TPS	Jumlah pemilih		
				L	P	L+P
1	Cianjur	11	519	62.835	63.223	126.058
2	Warungkondang	11	218	28.611	27.975	56.586
3	Cibeber	18	384	49.981	48.727	98.708
4	Cilaku	10	342	42.748	42.492	85.240
5	Ciranjang	9	254	32.279	31.838	64.117
6	Bojongpicung	11	232	31.224	30.774	61.998
7	Karangtengah	16	468	57.987	57.706	115.639
8	Mande	12	230	29.291	28.316	57.607
9	Sukaluyu	10	256	32.979	31.891	64.870
10	Pacet	7	308	40.673	38.161	78.834
11	Cugenang	16	345	44.152	41.450	85.602
12	Cikalongkulon	18	306	39.968	38.076	78.044
13	Sukaesmi	11	259	35.339	32.804	68.143
14	Sukanagara	10	172	21.188	20.440	42.628
15	Campaka	11	206	27.056	25.632	52.688
16	Takokak	9	163	21.081	20.527	41.608
17	Kadupandak	14	156	20.482	19.767	40.249
18	Pagelaran	14	231	29.644	28.817	58.461
19	Tanggeung	12	165	18.920	18.759	37.679
20	Cibinong	14	191	24.715	23.717	48.432
21	Sindangbarang	11	188	22.194	21.803	43.997
22	Agrabinta	11	124	16.041	15.577	31.618
23	Cidaun	14	209	27.797	26.913	54.710

24	Naringgul	11	140	19.069	17.425	36.494
25	Campakamulya	5	73	9.781	9.392	19.173
26	Cikadu	10	112	14.966	14.050	29.016
27	Gekbrong	8	172	22.383	21.469	43.854
28	Cipanas	7	350	42.534	40.000	82.534
29	Cijati	10	107	13.239	13.382	26.567
30	Leles	12	104	12.892	12.842	25.734
31	Haurwangi	8	182	23.996	23.090	47.086
32	Pasirkuda	9	112	15.122	14.435	29.552
	TOTAL	360	7.278	931.167	901.416	1.832.583

Sumber: jdih.kpu.go.id

Based on this data, the total permanent voter list (DPT) in Cianjur district is 1,832,583. This figure is a very large number so there needs to be an effort made by the Cianjur Regency KPUD in achieving the desired level of participation in the implementation of the 2024 elections. In this case, the Cianjur district KPUD targets the participation rate in the 2024 election to reach 80%.

After the general election was held on February 14, 2024, the KPUD of Cianjur Regency, West Java, recorded that the public participation rate reached around 75.7 percent of the total voting rights on the permanent voter list (DPT) of Cianjur Regency. The voter participation rate in the 2024 election is very far from what is targeted by the Cianjur Regency KPUD, which is 80%. The voter participation rate in Cianjur Regency was also recorded as the district with the lowest participation increase rate in West Java, which only increased by 0.7% from the 2019 election with a participation rate of around 75%. This figure is certainly very minimal and not in accordance with the target of 80 percent of the DPT of 1,832,583 voters, for this reason it is necessary to have political education carried out by the KPUD in Cianjur district in an effort to increase public participation in the upcoming elections.

The Cianjur Regency Regional Election Commission as the organizer of elections at the regional level has a strategic role in encouraging community participation. Various strategies have been carried out by the Cianjur KPUD to increase public awareness and involvement in every stage of the election. These strategies include direct socialization to the community, counseling through mass media and social media, as well as cooperation with community leaders, community organizations, and educational institutions. In addition, the Cianjur KPUD also takes an approach by targeting certain groups of voters, such as novice voters, women, people with disabilities, and indigenous peoples.

Although these various strategies have been implemented, the voter participation rate in the last election in Cianjur Regency still did not reach the expected target, which is 80%. Based on available data, the voter participation rate only reached 75.7%. This shows that the strategy implemented by the Cianjur Regency KPUD has not been fully effective in reaching and motivating all levels of society to exercise their voting rights. This low participation can be caused by several factors, such as the lack of public understanding of the importance of elections, low trust in the election process and results, and limited innovation in the socialization methods used by the KPUD. Based on this description, this study aims to examine in depth the strategies implemented by the Regional General Election Commission in an effort to increase public political participation in general elections in Cianjur Regency, as well as identify various obstacles faced by the KPU in the implementation of the strategy.

2. METHOD

In this study, the researcher used a qualitative descriptive method. (Hadi et al., 2021) Qualitative research is scientific research that aims to understand phenomena in a social context naturally, focusing on the process of deep interaction between the researcher and the phenomenon being studied. The location of this research was conducted at the General Election Commission (KPU) Office of Cianjur Regency which is located in Babakan Karet Village, Cianjur District, Cianjur Regency, West Java. In addition, the researcher also conducted interviews with several informants with different locations. The data collection techniques used by the researcher are literature studies, observations, interviews, and documentation. Furthermore, the techniques used by the researcher include:

1. Data Reduction

Data reduction is to re-examine and group data according to the issue being researched. After the selection, data that is in accordance with the research objectives will be explained in the form of a narrative, thus providing a clear and thorough understanding of the problem discussed (Subagyo & Kristian, 2023).

2. Data Presentation

This analysis is carried out by presenting data in the form of a description, where the researcher explains the data findings through organized sentences, including diagrams, and describing the relationships between categories in a structured and systematic manner (Subagyo & Kristian, 2023).

3. Conclusion

Initial conclusions are temporary and can change over time and data collection continues, but these conclusions can be considered credible if supported by

valid and consistent data (Miawaty, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Regional Election Commission Strategy in Increasing Political Participation in Elections in Cianjur Regency

Mintzberg in (Sitokdana & Tanaamah, 2016) said that strategy is an integrated pattern or plan of organizational goals. Meanwhile, the concept of strategy according to Salusu in (Giswanti, 2018) is an art in utilizing the skills and resources owned by an organization to achieve its goals, through effective relationships with the environment, by utilizing the most favorable conditions. According to Chandler (1962), organizational strategy consists of three main dimensions that are interrelated and must be considered simultaneously so that organizational goals can be achieved effectively.

The first dimension is long-term formulation and goals. In this dimension, the organization sets the vision, mission, and strategic goals to be achieved in a long period of time. The second dimension is the selection of actions. Once long-term goals are set, organizations need to determine the concrete steps to take to achieve those goals. The selection of actions includes decisions about the program or activities to be carried out, the method of implementation, and the communication approach to involve various related parties. The third dimension is resource allocation. The strategy will not succeed without adequate resource support and good management. Therefore, the organization must allocate the available resources effectively and efficiently according to the needs of the implementation of the chosen action.

1. Formulation and Long-Term Goals

As a general election commission, one of the tasks is to increase public participation, especially among novice voters to use their voting rights as well as possible. In this formulation and long-term target, the Cianjur Regency KPUD carries out its strategy by conducting socialization to novice voters, this can be seen from the results of a direct interview at the Cianjur Regency KPUD Office with Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, on April 28, 2025 at 08.00 WIB – 09.45 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it can be seen that one of the strategies in the formulation and long-term goals is targeted at novice voters, seeing the importance of the role of novice voters who in the future can not only play a role as voters but also as participants or implementers. In addition to conducting interviews, the researcher also made observations, based on the results of observations, it showed that the Cianjur Regency KPUD often conducted socialization and collaborated with several schools to conduct political education. The Cianjur Regency Regional General Election Commission has collaborated with several

schools and educational institutions in the context of socializing the 2024 Election, especially to increase the participation of novice voters. This is in line with what was said by Mr. Dr. H. Dedi Mulyadi, S.H., M.H. as an academic as a Lecturer at the Faculty of Law, Suryakencana University in Cianjur, on May 5, 2025 at 10.00 WIB – 11.00 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, the researcher described that the Cianjur Regency KPUD carried out its long-term formulation and goals through socialization and political education strategies for generation Z or novice voters by visiting several schools in Cianjur Regency.

2. Action Selection

The selection of this action can also be said to be a determination of socialization actions with several segments, as expressed by the informant Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of the Subdivision of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, on April 28, 2025 at 08.00 WIB – 09.45 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it can be seen that the Cianjur Regency KPUD not only carries out its strategy to novice voters but also to the general public and villages with a low level of community participation in the General Election process.

In addition to conducting interviews, the author also made observations related to the election care village or DP3 which is a program of the Cianjur Regency KPUD. The Election and Election Care Village Program (DP3) is an initiative of the Cianjur Regency KPUD to increase community political participation at the village level, especially in areas with low participation rates. This program aims to build public awareness and understanding of the importance of participating in elections and elections. In the selection of this action, the Cianjur Regency KPUD also took advantage of the use of mass media in carrying out its strategy as said by Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of the Subdivision of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of the Subdivision of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, on April 28, 2025 at 08.00 WIB – 09.45 WIB.

Based on the results of the interview, it can be seen that the Cianjur Regency KPUD is also active in using social media, so that the public can get all information about the election through the media owned by the Cianjur Regency KPUD. In addition to carrying out some of these actions, the Cianjur Regency KPUD also carried out the Election Carnival program during the General Election stage. With this Election Carnival, the Cianjur Regency KPUD hopes that the people involved in this carnival activities can become more aware of their rights and obligations as voters. This can encourage people to be more active in the political process and elections.

3. Resource Allocation

The allocation of these resources is also related to the ability of the organization to carry out activities related to the resources owned by the KPUD. Based on the results of the interview with Mr. Sanatha Perguna as the Head of the Technical Sub-Division, it can be seen that the Cianjur Regency Regional General Election Commission conducts a planned and structured allocation of human resources, budget, and logistics with technical guidance, socialization, and determination of strategic polling stations is an important step to ensure the implementation of effective, efficient, and participatory elections. In the Election stages, the Cianjur Regency KPUD is assisted by PPK and PPS spread across each sub-district and village in Cianjur Regency.

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted on the implementation of the election stages by the Cianjur Regency Regional General Election Commission (KPUD), it can be seen that resource allocation is one of the crucial aspects that is carefully planned by the KPUD. This resource management includes three main aspects, namely human resources, budget, and logistics, which are the foundation in supporting the sustainability of each stage of the election. From observations in the field, it can be seen that the Cianjur Regency KPUD shows adaptive and responsive organizational capacity, through cooperation with ad-hoc bodies and a participatory approach in the election process. Close coordination between the KPUD, PPK, and PPS accompanied by ongoing training reflects strategic and planned resource management, with the ultimate goal of creating effective, efficient, and participatory elections.

B. Obstacles faced by the Regional General Election Commission in increasing political participation in elections in Cianjur Regency

In an effort to increase public political participation in the elections in Cianjur Regency, the Cianjur Regency Regional General Election Commission faces various obstacles that hinder the achievement of this goal. Based on the results of the research conducted, some of the main obstacles faced by KPUD include:

1. The geographical conditions of Cianjur are very wide

Based on the results of the interviews obtained, it is known that this diversity has a direct impact on accessibility and connectivity between regions, especially to the southern regions which tend to be more remote and have road infrastructure that is not as good as the central and northern regions, this condition makes the implementation of political education and socialization activities require more time and cost than in urban or lowland areas. Political education and socialization programs must of course be adjusted to the available budget allocation. High logistics costs in the southern region ranging from transportation, accommodation, to the procurement of infrastructure facilities are a limiting factor. If not managed

with the right strategy, this can lead to decreased program effectiveness.

In addition to conducting interviews, the researcher also made observations related to the geographical conditions of Cianjur Regency. The statement is very logical and can be justified based on the geographical, structural, and technical realities faced by the Cianjur Regency KPU. The size of the area, difficult access, the limitations of supporting structures outside the election stage, and the limitation of budget and resources are real obstacles that directly limit the effectiveness of political education strategies, especially in the southern Cianjur region. Based on an interview with Mr. Dr. H. Dedi Mulyadi., S.H., M.H. as a Lecturer at the Faculty of Law, Suryakencana University, it can be concluded that the geographical condition of Cianjur is indeed a serious challenge to the effectiveness of political education. Therefore, KPUD is highly recommended to develop strategies that are relevant to the local context, one of which is by maximizing social media as an alternative medium of socialization. This strategy is considered more efficient in terms of budget and able to reach the wider community, especially young voters in areas that are difficult to reach physically.

2. Public distrust of the government

Based on the results of the interview with Mr. Ifan Yuspian as the Head of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, it can be found that sociological and empirical facts are often found in the context of remote areas such as South Cianjur. Not only geographical conditions are a challenge, but also low public trust in the government, lack of political literacy, and more urgent economic priorities due to the lack of education and socialization provided. All of this has led to low levels of political participation and made the election socialization program a more complex challenge. This is also strengthened by a statement from a farmer in the southern Cianjur area, the researcher conducted an interview with one of the farmers named Sukandi on May 12, 2025 at 19.00 – 19.30 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it can be seen that there are still some people who are more concerned with work affairs than participating in election activities, especially a farmer, in this case the Cianjur Regency KPUD must be able to encourage and educate them regarding their important role in the implementation of the General Election.

3. Limited resources

Based on the results of an interview with Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, it can be seen that the Cianjur Regency Regional General Election Commission no longer contracts employees either in the non-election stage process or in the election stage process. Previously, the Cianjur Regency KPUD could recruit

contract workers to support the election stages. This is often done by recruiting additional workforce that is prioritized to support specific divisions during the election process. This is done to meet the needs of the workforce that are temporary and dynamic, along with the complex stages of the election. However, after a regulation from PAN-RB (Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform) that prohibits government agencies from recruiting contract workers after 2020, this policy has a big impact on KPUD in terms of workforce management. This decision aims to reduce the use of contract labor in the long term and prioritize the use of civil servants or a more permanent staffing system.

C. Efforts made by the Cianjur Regency KPUD in overcoming existing obstacles

1. Overcoming Geographical Constraints

After conducting an interview related to how the obstacles faced by the Cianjur Regency KPUD, the researcher also conducted an interview related to how the efforts made by the Cianjur Regency KPUD in overcoming the existing obstacles to Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, on April 28, 2025 at 08.00 WIB – 09.45 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that the Cianjur Regency KPUD faces geographical challenges in distributing election information throughout the region. To overcome these obstacles, KPUD implements a dual communication strategy, namely by maximizing the use of social media in collaboration with ad-hoc bodies such as PPK and PPS, as well as optimizing traditional media such as banners and billboards placed in strategic locations, including village offices. This strategy reflects the KPUD's efforts to reach out to the wider community, especially in remote areas, to increase the effectiveness of socialization and voter participation in elections.

2. Overcoming Public Distrust of the Government

In an effort to overcome public distrust of the government, the researcher conducted a direct interview with Mr. Ipan Yuspian as the Head of Participation, Public Relations and Human Resources, on April 28, 2025 at 08.00 WIB – 09.45 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that the Cianjur Regency KPUD has a program called DP3. In the DP3 (Election and Election Care Village) program organized by the Cianjur Regency KPUD, the material provided is designed to increase public knowledge, awareness, and political participation.

3. Overcoming resource limitations

In an effort to overcome resource limitations, the researcher conducted a direct interview with Mr. Sanatha Perguna as the Head of the Technical

Sub-Division, Election Implementation and Law, on May 2, 2025 at 08.30 WIB – 09.45 WIB. Based on the results of the interview, it was found that the Technical Guidance (Bimtek) material provided by the Cianjur Regency KPUD to adhoc bodies (PPK, PPS, KPSS) aims to increase the capacity of election organizers at the sub-district and village levels, as well as support the increase in community political participation.

Discussion

A. Long-term formulation and goals

Political participation is defined as a term that refers to the involvement of citizens or community activities that aim to influence or change the existing power structure in the political field (Munawarah & Kristanto, 2022). The results of interviews and observations show that the Cianjur Regency KPUD consistently carries out a long-term strategy that focuses on increasing the participation of novice voters, especially generation Z, in the democratic process. The main strategy used is to conduct intensive socialization and political education in the environment of high schools and other educational institutions. This approach is very relevant and strategic considering that novice voters are a group that will use their voting rights for the first time. Socialization activities carried out by KPUD in schools such as MAN 2 Cianjur and SMAN 1 Cianjur aim to equip students with knowledge about the stages of elections, how to vote correctly, and the importance of participation so that they do not get caught. In addition, cooperation with various elements of society such as the Scout Movement and special Islamic boarding schools for people with disabilities indicates that the Cianjur Regency KPUD is also trying to reach out to special groups and ensure equitable accessibility of election information for all levels of society.

B. Action Selection

Based on the results of interviews and observations, the Cianjur Regency KPUD implements a multifaceted socialization strategy and targets various segments of society, not only limited to novice voters, but also the general public and residents in villages with low participation rates. According to Anderson in the book *Communication Planning and Strategy* (Canggara, 2013) stated that strategy can be understood as an art that involves the intellectual ability to manage and utilize all available resources to achieve goals in an efficient way and optimize profits. This inclusive approach shows the KPUD awareness of the diversity of characteristics and information needs of different communities in the Cianjur Regency area. The Election and Election Care Village (DP3) program is one of the important innovations that shows that the KPUD is focused on increasing political participation in villages with low participation rates. The selection of villages that are the target of this program based on previous participation data is an effective strategic step to allocate resources appropriately. The formation of DP3 cadres in villages such as Sindangsari, Kanoman, and Cikidangbayabang provides hope for the sustainable

dissemination of information from people who have received education to the wider community.

The use of social media as one of the socialization channels is a very relevant and strategic step, especially to reach generation Z and novice voters who tend to be more familiar with digital technology. The activities of the KPUD on platforms such as Instagram and the obligation of the PPK and PPS to have social media strengthen efforts to disseminate information more widely and quickly. In addition, collaboration with various stakeholders, such as journalists, media organizations, local governments, and political parties, further strengthens the KPUD's communication network. The socialization of the election stages to journalists and the plan to provide media centers show the KPUD's efforts to ensure transparency, accountability, and accurate information dissemination to the public. The Election Carnival activity is a form of real action that prioritizes direct interaction between election organizers and the community at various strategic points, such as schools, traditional markets, and car free days. This carnival is also a symbolic medium that strengthens democratic identity through the use of KPUD flags and patakas.

C. Resource Allocation

The results of the study show that the allocation of resources by the Cianjur Regency KPUD in the implementation of elections is carried out in a planned and structured manner, including human resources, budget, and logistics. In terms of human resources, intensive recruitment and coaching of ad-hoc bodies such as the Voting Committee (PPS) and the Voting Organizing Group (KPPS) are an important foundation to ensure that the election runs smoothly and effectively. From the budget aspect, the allocation of funds which includes officer honorarium and other operational costs shows that the Cianjur Regency KPUD understands the importance of providing adequate incentives to maintain the motivation and performance of organizing officers. Similarly, logistics management such as the strategic location of Polling Stations (TPS) is of special concern so that voters can easily access polling stations, increasing the possibility of public participation in elections.

D. Obstacles faced by the Cianjur Regency KPUD

According to Arbi Sanit in (Sandabunga, 2019) there are three functions of political participation, namely providing appreciation and support to the rulers, the government that is formed, and the political system they run; as an effort to reveal the weaknesses and shortcomings that exist in the government; and forms of resistance {in the form of demonstrations, riots, or even coups} against the ruler with the aim of overthrowing him, which is expected to encourage structural changes in the government and political system. The results of the study revealed that in an effort to increase community political participation in Cianjur Regency, KPUD faced several significant obstacles stemming from various factors, including:

1. The geographical conditions of Cianjur Regency, which are very wide and diverse, are the main obstacles. This district has areas with very different access, ranging from mountainous areas to the seacoast, especially the remote southern area with limited road infrastructure. This causes limitations in reaching the community physically, so that the process of socialization and political education becomes more complicated and requires much greater cost and time than in urban areas.
2. Low public trust in the government and lack of political literacy are also factors that hinder participation. Interview data revealed a tendency for people, especially in remote areas such as South Cianjur, to prioritize daily economic activities such as farming rather than participating in the election process. This condition is exacerbated by a lack of education about the importance of political participation and the lack of information they obtain.
3. The limitation of human resources within the Cianjur Regency KPUD is a serious challenge in the implementation of activities to increase political participation. The change in policy from the Ministry of PAN RB which prohibits government agencies from recruiting contract workers after 2020 has a significant impact on the capacity of KPU human resources.

Overall, geographical constraints, community culture, and resource limitations are multidimensional challenges that require a holistic and adaptive approach from the Cianjur Regency KPUD. Conventional socialization strategies need to be complemented by digital technology-based innovations to reach groups of voters who are physically difficult to reach.

E. Efforts made by the Cianjur Regency KPUD

1. Overcoming Geographical Constraints

The Cianjur Regency KPUD showed quite effective strategy adaptation, such as the use of social media to disseminate election information that can reach the community more widely and cheaply; active collaboration with adhoc bodies (PPK and PPS) in distributing information to the public directly through traditional media such as billboards and banners tailored to the cultural context and access to local information; and coordination with the village government in the strategic placement of the PPS secretariat so as to facilitate public access to election information and services. This strategy shows an adaptive and collaborative approach, where the KPUD does not work alone, but empowers existing structural networks.

2. Overcoming Public Distrust of the Government

The low level of public trust in the government, especially in remote areas, is an obstacle to increasing political participation. To overcome this, the Cianjur

Regency KPUD implements the DP3 Program (Election and Election Care Village) which directly targets people in villages with low participation. The material presented in this program is very comprehensive, ranging from the introduction of democracy to ethics in elections. In addition to providing substantive knowledge, DP3 also has a psychological dimension in rebuilding public trust in the importance of their role in determining the direction of government.

3. Overcoming Resource Limitations

The limited number of permanent employees within the Cianjur Regency KPUD, which only totals 27 people, is a big challenge in facing the complexity of the election stages, especially after the ban on the recruitment of contract workers by the central government. Efforts are made to overcome these limitations by optimizing the role of adhoc bodies through training and technical guidance (Technical Guidance). This step reflects efforts to improve efficiency and improve the quality of human resources, although the quantity remains limited. With targeted training, the Cianjur KPUD seeks to compensate for the shortage of personnel through improving the competence and work effectiveness of adhoc bodies spread across all sub-districts and villages.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research on the strategy of the Regional General Election Commission in increasing political participation in elections in Cianjur Regency, as well as the obstacles faced in its implementation, it can be concluded that the Cianjur Regency KPUD has implemented a comprehensive and adaptive strategy. The strategy includes political education for novice voters (especially generation Z) through socialization activities to schools and educational institutions; the implementation of the Election and Election Care Village (DP3) program targeting villages with low participation rates; and the use of social media to reach young voters and people in areas that are difficult to access physically. In addition, KPUD also optimizes the use of traditional media such as billboards and banners, collaborates with community leaders and village governments, organizes field activities such as Election Carnivals to strengthen relationships with the community, and strengthens the capacity of adhoc bodies (PPK, PPS, and KPPS) through comprehensive technical guidance. However, the implementation of the strategy cannot be separated from a number of obstacles that affect its effectiveness. These obstacles include geographical conditions that make it difficult to access information, low public trust in the government and lack of political literacy, limited human resources due to the policy of prohibiting the recruitment of contract workers from the central government, and budget and time constraints, especially during the non-election period, which limits the intensity of socialization activities. Nevertheless, the Cianjur Regency KPUD has made efforts to overcome these challenges through cross-sector collaboration, digitalization of socialization,

intensive training for adhoc bodies, and educational approaches tailored to the local conditions of the community.

From these findings, the author suggests that KPUD strengthen community-based socialization by involving various elements of the village community to increase the effectiveness of political communication. Political literacy also needs to be improved on an ongoing basis through programs such as the Democracy Class or the Young Voter Forum. In addition, the use of information technology and social media must be optimized with educational content that is interesting and easy to understand. Finally, the capacity and welfare of adhoc bodies need to be improved through applicable training and incentive evaluation to support optimal performance.

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